

1 **Illuminating the Hierarchical Segmentation of Faults through an**
2 **Unsupervised Learning Approach applied to Seismic Sequences**
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12 **Key points**

- 13 • We present a workflow to reveal segmented fault surfaces within hypocenter
14 distributions through unsupervised learning algorithms
15 • Comparison with earthquake focal mechanisms corroborates the procedure
16 • A hierarchical order of planar fault segments associated with different types of
17 faulting is derived
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21 **Abstract**

22 We propose a workflow for the recognition of the hierarchical segmentation of faults through
23 earthquake hypocenter clustering without prior information. Our approach combines density-
24 based clustering algorithms (DBSCAN and OPTICS), and principal component analysis
25 (PCA). Given a spatial distribution of earthquake hypocenters, DBSCAN identifies first-order
26 clusters, representing regions with the highest density of connected seismic events. Within
27 each first-order cluster, OPTICS further identifies nested higher-order clusters, providing
28 information on their number and size. PCA analysis is applied to first- and higher-order
29 clusters to evaluate eigenvalues, allowing discrimination between seismicity associated with
30 planar features and distributed seismicity that remains uncategorized. The identified planes
31 are then geometrically characterized in terms of their location and orientation in the space,
32 length, and height. This automated procedure operates within two spatial scales: the largest
33 scale corresponds to the longest pattern of approximately equally dense earthquake clouds,
34 while the smallest scale relates to earthquake location errors. By applying PCA analysis
35 before and after OPTICS, a planar feature outputted from a first-order cluster can be
36 interpreted as a fault surface while planes outputted after OPTICS can be interpreted as fault
37 segments comprised within the fault surface. The evenness between the orientation of
38 illuminated fault surfaces and fault segments, and that of the nodal planes of earthquake focal
39 mechanisms calculated along the same faults, corroborates this interpretation. Our workflow
40 has been successfully applied to earthquake hypocenter distributions from various seismically
41 active areas (Italy, Taiwan, California) associated with faults exhibiting diverse kinematics.

42 **Plain Language Summary**

43 Active faults are associated with ongoing movement and seismic activity. Recognizing them
44 within large clouds of earthquake hypocenters is at the same time challenging and crucial for
45 seismic hazard estimates. Here, we present a new procedure that can illuminate fault surfaces
46 and its constituting segments by exclusively using hypocenter locations and their spatial
47 density. We apply our approach to hypocenter distributions from various seismically active
48 areas (Italy, Taiwan, California). The evenness between the orientation of illuminated fault
49 surfaces and fault segments, and that derived from other data sources, corroborates our
50 workflow. This workflow is showed to be an effective tool to derive unbiased fault
51 geometries. It also offers new perspectives for the study of the relationships between seismic
52 activity patterns and fault segment interactions, as well as seismic forecasting.

53

54 **1 Introduction**

55 Geological faults, regardless their kinematics, but in most cases are complex
56 structures comprising multiple fault segments (Wesnousky, 1988; Nicol et al., 2002; Walsh et
57 al., 2003; Childs et al., 2009; Manighetti et al., 2009; Delogkos et al., 2020; Camanni et al.,
58 2019; Roche et al., 2021; Camanni et al., 2023a, b). In seismically active areas, fault
59 segmentation has been shown to have a significant impact on how a co-seismic rupture
60 nucleates and propagates during an earthquake (Wesnousky, 1988, 2006; Manighetti et al.,
61 2007, 2009; Hu et al., 2016; Nissen et al., 2016; Perrin et al., 2016; Cesca et al., 2017; Li and
62 Liu, 2020; Roche et al., 2022). When an earthquake rupture progresses on a segmented fault
63 and reaches a fault segment boundary, it can either stop propagating or jump to an adjacent
64 segment, depending on the distance between adjacent segments (Wesnousky, 1988, 2006;
65 Yikilmaz et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2020). Consequently, a comprehensive knowledge of the
66 segmentation of an active fault is fundamental for seismic hazard assessment and earthquake

67 forecasting of an active region (Field et al., 2003; Boncio et al., 2004; Woessner et al., 2015;
68 Martinez-Garzon et al., 2015; Chartier et al., 2019; Bello et al., 2022).

69 In seismically active areas, one approach that can be used for illuminating fault surfaces is by
70 analyzing earthquake hypocenter spatial distributions (Ouillon et al., 2008; Ouillon &
71 Sornette, 2011; Kaven et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2013; Kamer et al., 2020; Brunsvick et al.,
72 2021; Truttmann et al., 2023). Associating earthquake hypocenters with fault surfaces is one
73 of the most challenging open issues in seismic hazard assessment, especially for areas where
74 auxiliary information from surface geology, borehole data and geophysical imaging is not
75 available. In the last decades, several methods based on clustering algorithms have been
76 proposed for achieving this. Partitional clustering such as k-means (Ouillon et al., 2008) and
77 Gaussian Mixture models (Ouillon & Sornette, 2011) have been used to group earthquakes in
78 clusters labelled as faults if the smallest principal component eigenvalue of every cluster is
79 less than the earthquake location error. An attempt to introduce uncertainty of the spatial
80 location of hypocenters using k-means clustering has been made by Wang et al. (2013).
81 Kamer et al. (2020) have proposed a sophisticated method for faults reconstruction based on
82 agglomerative hierarchical clustering where faults are modelled by Gaussian kernels, which
83 are merged until the information gain measured in terms of a Bayesian criterion is positive.
84 Consecutive application of spectral clustering (Von Luxburg, 2007) and density-based
85 clustering (Ester et al., 1996) have been used by Brunsvik et al. (2021) to reconstruct the
86 main Paganica fault system activated during L'Aquila 2009 seismic sequence. An open-
87 source toolbox built on density-based clustering has been provided by Petersen et al. (2021)
88 to reconstruct the first-order geometry of faults. A visual analysis approach that uses an
89 algorithm based on singular value decomposition to fit planar surfaces has been developed by
90 Wang et al. (2019). Truttmann et al. (2023) have introduced a method for 3D imaging of
91 faults that combines nearest neighbor learning and principal component analysis with a
92 Monte Carlo-based approach to account for hypocenter relocation uncertainties.

93 While some of these studies focus on developing methods to also describe complex fault
94 structures, they often do not fully address the hierarchical segmentation of the retrieved
95 faults. The overarching goal of this work is to make this step forward by means of a new
96 method based on an unsupervised learning approach (HSF-ULA).

97 Specifically, we propose a workflow based on the combined use of two density-based
98 clustering algorithms, DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) and OPTICS (Ankerst et al., 1999), and
99 principal component analysis, PCA, (Pearson, 1901). Using in combination these clustering
100 algorithms allows us to derive not only information on large-scale faults (through DBSCAN),
101 but also, once they are defined, to derive the geometry of the fault segments comprised within
102 it (through OPTICS).

103 Unlike previous approaches, where fault segment identification depends on operator-made
104 assumptions (for example, mechanically halving the cluster size (e.g. Ouillon et al., 2008) or
105 assigning a probability to each data and assuming that the segments are well described by
106 Gaussian kernels (e.g. Ouillon & Sornette, 2011, Kamer et al., 2020), the new approach
107 proposed here ensures that the fault segmentation hierarchy is not operator-dependent, but
108 solely relies on the spatial density of the data.

109 The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we describe the proposed workflow
110 and provide details on how location, size and orientation of planar surfaces are retrieved. In
111 sec. 3, we apply the workflow to different areas (Italy, Taiwan, California) where faults
112 exhibit diverse kinematics (extensional, reverse, strike-slip). For each case, a table with the
113 results for first and second order planar surfaces is provided, while the results for the main
114 third-order features are provided in the supporting information. In sec. 4, a comparison is

115 made between the orientation of illuminated fault surfaces and that of the nodal planes of
116 earthquake focal mechanisms calculated along the same faults. Finally, in sec. 5 we discuss
117 the obtained results and outline potential and limitations of the proposed procedure.

118

119 **2 Methods**

120 The proposed automated workflow is illustrated in Fig. 1. To illuminate fault surfaces
121 in a given earthquake hypocenter catalog, the first step consists in performing a cluster
122 analysis by DBSCAN (Fig. 1). The application of DBSCAN allows us to illuminate first-
123 order clusters with the highest number of density-connected seismic events. This algorithm
124 requires two inputs: ϵ , the neighborhood radius, and Z , the threshold minimum value for the
125 number of points in the ϵ -neighborhood. Based on the values of ϵ and Z , DBSCAN groups
126 together into clusters only density-connected hypocenters, i.e. hypocenters whose
127 neighborhoods contain at least Z hypocenters that are in the ϵ -neighborhood of each other or
128 lying on their boundaries; all the rest of hypocenters is considered noise and discarded from
129 the cluster analysis. By varying ϵ and Z , DBSCAN provides a very large number of different
130 solutions, which can be divided into five classes according to Piegari et al. (2022). We choose
131 a solution in the class named Crossover Region (CR). This class includes the cluster solutions
132 that simultaneously satisfy the two conditions: i) number of noise points $< 60\%$ and ii)
133 number of points belonging to the biggest cluster $< 60\%$. These solutions vary little in terms
134 of number and size of the clusters and maximize the number of the largest clusters. This is the
135 reason why we start by considering one of them, as it allows us to illuminate the biggest
136 number of (first-order) clusters. We point out that the choice to start from an internal solution
137 to the CR is determined solely by the preference to divide the dataset into the greatest number
138 of primary structures but does not affect the fault segmentation hierarchy, which is dependent
139 only on the spatial distribution of the data.

140 In the next step, to define whether or not a first-order cluster can be associated to a planar
141 feature, a principal component analysis (PCA) is performed (Fig. 1). We note that, even if a
142 data scaling is used to illuminate the biggest clusters and retrieve the cluster indices, PCA is
143 applied to the original dataset and not to the scaled dataset. PCA is classified as an
144 unsupervised machine learning algorithm for linear dimensionality reduction. It consists in
145 diagonalizing the covariance matrix, i.e. finding a new basis of coordinates aligned with the
146 directions that maximize the data variation from the mean. The three eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$
147 correspond to the variance of the data in the new (decorrelated) reference system. Following
148 Ouillon et al. (2008), if the two largest eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 are larger than location errors e
149 and are much larger than the third one λ_3 , the cluster geometrically defines a planar feature
150 (Fig. 1). Within this plane (or if the condition $\lambda_3 \ll \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ is not satisfied for the first-order
151 cluster), the algorithm OPTICS is then applied to investigate its internal hierarchy, for the
152 identification of density-based, second-order, nested clusters (Fig. 1).

153 The output of OPTICS is a type of graph called reachability plot, which visualizes the
154 reachability distance of each point in the dataset. Points belonging to a cluster have a low
155 reachability distance to their nearest neighbor and are recognizable as valleys in the
156 reachability plot. The deeper the valleys, the denser the clusters. Valleys are separated by
157 peaks, which are points in the dataset that are at relatively longer distances from their
158 neighbors. Therefore, peaks in the reachability plot can be associated with transitions from
159 one cluster to another and give information about the presence of different density regions
160 within the data. Once the reachability plot is generated, second-order clusters are extracted
161 manually by setting a threshold on the y-axis that cuts off the valleys.

162 PCA is iteratively applied to second-order clusters corresponding to each valley. For each of
 163 such second-order clusters, if the condition $\lambda_3 \ll \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ is satisfied, a planar feature is built.
 164 OPTICS is then further applied for the identification of third-order planar features within
 165 second-order ones, etc., up to the condition for planar geometry is not satisfied or the
 166 eigenvalues are smaller than location errors.

167 We emphasize that the only algorithm of the workflow that is computationally expensive is
 168 OPTICS. This is one of the reasons why we introduce its use only after the identification of
 169 the main first-order largest clusters is made. In this way, the initial amount of data is reduced
 170 by a percentage of noise data, which are discarded, and it is conveniently divided into subsets
 171 that are more easy to manage.

172 For characterizing the geometry of a recognized planar feature, the two eigenvectors \mathbf{u}_1 and
 173 \mathbf{u}_2 , corresponding to the eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 (i.e., the two principal components,
 174 determined by PCA) are used. The plane defining equation can be written in terms of the
 175 orthonormal eigenvector $\mathbf{u}_3 = \mathbf{n}$ related to the third eigenvalues λ_3 as:

$$176 \quad \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_C = 0 ,$$

177 where \mathbf{x} is a point that lie on the plane and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_C$ is the cluster barycenter. The third eigenvector
 178 \mathbf{n} can be also used to compute the strike (azimuth of a horizontal line lying on the plane) and
 179 dip (angle of maximum inclination of the plane) angles of the plane as follows (Quinn and
 180 Ehlmann, 2019):

$$181 \quad \text{strike} = \tan^{-1} \frac{n_1}{n_2} - \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$182 \quad \text{dip} = \cos^{-1} \frac{n_3}{\|\mathbf{n}\|}$$

185 where n_1, n_2 and n_3 are the components of the vector \mathbf{n} . The dimensions (length and height) of
 186 the planes depend on data variability along the directions \mathbf{u}_1 and \mathbf{u}_2 and thus can be expressed
 187 as functions of λ_1 and λ_2 . According to Ouillon et al. (2008), for sake of simplicity we
 188 assume that hypocenter locations are uniformly distributed over the planes. If x is a 1D
 189 continuous random variable whose values are uniformly distributed on the interval $[a, b]$, its
 190 variance is given by:

$$191 \quad \text{Var}(x) = \int_a^b (x - \mu)^2 \frac{1}{b - a} dx = \frac{(b - a)^2}{12}$$

192 where $\mu = (a + b)/2$. Generalizing this formula to a 2D case, it follows that an
 193 approximation for the length L and the height H of the fault planes can be obtained by the
 194 equations: $L = \sqrt{12\lambda_1}$, $H = \sqrt{12\lambda_2}$.

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201 **Figure 1.** Flow diagram of the **HSF-ULA** workflow.

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203 3 Application of HSF-ULA to case studies

204 3.1 Case 1: clouds of earthquake hypocenters associated with extensional faults (Italy)

205 As an example of application to a normal fault system, we test the developed workflow by
 206 illuminating planar surfaces within the hypocenter distribution of the 2009 L'Aquila (Italy)
 207 seismic sequence (Chiari et al., 2012, Lavecchia et al., 2012, Brunsvick et al., 2021). We
 208 use the high-resolution earthquake catalog by Valoroso et al. (2013, 2020), which consists of
 209 64051 events spanning from 2009-01-07 to 2009-12-20.

210 In Fig. 2a, it is shown a DBSCAN cluster solution in the CR corresponding to values of the
 211 input parameters $\epsilon = 0.5$ km and $Z = 200$. Note that before applying DBSCAN, we translated
 212 the horizontal coordinates to the hypocenter depth range (2.3 – 21.3 km) using the min-max
 213 scaling, which allowed us to consider the spatial anisotropy of the distribution (Piegari et al.,
 214 2022). The algorithm automatically illuminates six first-order clusters and discards about
 215 12% of events classified as noise (gray points in Fig. 2a). For brevity, we apply PCA only to
 216 the two largest first-order clusters (light blue and light green color points in Fig. 2) related to
 217 L'Aquila and Campotosto faults (Brunsvick et al., 2021), respectively. The results of the
 218 applications of PCA with the corresponding geometrical parameters for the reconstructed
 219 planar features are reported in Table 1, and the planes are illustrated in Fig. 2b. In addition, to
 220 look for second-order clusters within C_1 and C_2 first-order-ones, OPTICS was applied.
 221 Results (Fig. 3) show that several second-order clusters can be built within first-order ones.
 222 Note that all of them can be assigned a planar feature except the smallest second-order cluster
 223 C_{14} for which the condition $\lambda_3 \ll \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ is not satisfied. Looking at the reachability plots in
 224 Figs. 3a and 3b, it is visible that many of the named valleys include other sub-valleys that can
 225 be associated to third-order clusters. The results of the investigation of the sub-clusters of C_{11}
 226 and C_{12} are reported in supplementary material, along with the animated gif of the 3D
 227 plots in Figs. 3c-e.

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231 **Figure 2.** A workflow application to L'Aquila seismic sequence. **a** A DBSCAN solution
232 illuminating six earthquake clusters ($Z = 200$ and $\epsilon = 0.5$ km). Gray points are earthquakes
233 discarded as noise points. **b** First-order planar surfaces retrieved by PCA are shown for the
234 two biggest clusters C_1 and C_2 .

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240 **Figure 3.** A workflow application to L'Aquila seismic sequence. In **a** and **b**, reachability plot
 241 for clusters C_1 and C_2 of Fig. 2, respectively. In **c** and **d**, DBSCAN solutions for C_1 ($\epsilon = 1$ km
 242 and $Z = 200$) and C_2 ($\epsilon = 1$ km and $Z = 200$) with planar surfaces retrieved from PCA,
 243 respectively. **e** A 3D view showing the seven second-order planes retrieved after two
 244 iterations of the procedure. The white and red traces at the surface correspond to the faults
 245 mapped at the surface in the L'Aquila area (Brunsvik et al., 2021). Earthquakes classified at
 246 each iteration as noise points are not shown.

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249 **Table 1** Geometrical parameters from PCA analysis applied to first-order clusters C_1 and C_2
 250 in Fig. 2 and related second-order clusters shown in Figs. 3c-e. Longitude, Latitude and
 251 Depth are those of the barycenter of the clusters.

252

Cluster order	Symbol	N	Longitude (°)	Latitude (°)	Depth (km)	L (km)	H (km)	Dip (°)	Strike (°)	λ_3 (km ²)
I (L'Aquila Fault)	C_1	31284	13.451	42.313	-5.7	25.2	8.4	38.9	144.4	0.6880
II (L'Aquila Fault)	C_{11}	18988	13.497	42.285	-4.7	10.3	6.1	29.6	129.5	0.6356
	C_{12}	8446	13.381	42.355	-7.6	10.4	5.4	49.4	140.4	0.1215
	C_{13}	1291	13.291	42.418	-7.9	5.3	2.1	41.7	142.1	0.1340
	C_{14}	328	13.435	42.347	-3.4	-	-	-	-	0.1378
I (Campotosto Fault)	C_2	11634	13.371	42.469	-8.3	18.0	8.0	19.7	151.1	0.6842
II (Campotosto Fault)	C_{21}	3517	13.389	42.449	-9.2	10.4	2.8	25.0	144.5	0.1607
	C_{22}	2871	13.380	42.493	-7.6	6.3	2.5	37.3	137.3	0.2068
	C_{23}	2491	13.383	42.411	-8.2	5.7	2.3	34.7	139.5	0.1482
	C_{24}	2080	13.324	42.532	-7.9	6.3	3.6	28.2	146.8	0.1572

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254 3.2 Case 2: clouds of earthquake hypocenters associated with a reverse fault (Taiwan)

255 Seismicity of the active Taiwan mountain belt is associated with faults with varying
 256 kinematics (Kuoehen et al., 2004, 2007; Wu et al., 2008a, b). We apply the workflow to a
 257 spatial distribution of 87679 earthquake hypocenters occurred in the period from 1990-01-01
 258 to 2020-12-31 in the southeastern sector of the mountain belt (UTM coordinates from 265.99

259 to 377.5 km Easting and from 2515.9 to 2578.4 km Northing), in an area comprised within
260 the Central and Coastal ranges of the mountain belt (Kuochen et al., 2004; 2007).

261 Fig. 4a shows a DBSCAN solution in the CR corresponding to $\varepsilon = 1$ km and $Z = 80$. It has
262 been obtained after scaling the horizontal coordinates to the hypocenter depth range (5 – 30
263 km) to take into account the spatial anisotropy of the distribution. This solution illuminates
264 the biggest, first-order clusters C_1 and C_2 , respectively. We focus our analysis on C_2 as it
265 well-know from the literature that seismicity within it belongs to the Chihshang Fault, a
266 reverse fault that was recently associated with the Mw 6.8 Chengkung earthquake occurred in
267 2003 (Angelier et al., 2000; Kuochen et al., 2007, 2004; Ching et al., 2007; Mozziconacci et
268 al., 2009). This cluster groups 16244 earthquakes and can be associated to a first-order planar
269 surface (see Fig. 4b) defined by the parameters in Table 2. Fig. 4c shows the reachability plot
270 of C_2 , with the cut line $\varepsilon = 2$ km that identifies the biggest valleys, i.e. two main second-order
271 clusters. Both of them can be associated to planar surfaces (see Fig. 4d), whose parameters
272 are reported in Table 3, and include several subvalleys. They are associated to third-order
273 clusters and are investigated in the supplementary material.

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276 **Figure 4.** A workflow application to Taiwan dataset. **a** A DBSCAN solution illuminating
277 eight earthquake clusters in a southeastern sector of Taiwan ($Z = 80$ and $\varepsilon = 1$ km). **b** First-
278 order planar surface retrieved by PCA is shown for the biggest cluster C_2 . **c** Reachability plot
279 of C_2 with the cut line $\varepsilon = 2$ km. **d** DBSCAN solution ($\varepsilon = 2$ km and $Z = 80$) with planar
280 surfaces retrieved by PCA. Earthquakes classified as noise points are shown only in the first
281 panel in gray color.

282

283 **Table 2** Geometrical parameters from PCA analysis applied to first-order cluster C_2 and
284 related second-order clusters shown in Fig. 4b and Fig. 4d. Longitude, Latitude and Depth are
285 those of the barycenter of the clusters.

286

Cluster order	Symbol	N	Longitude (°)	Latitude (°)	Depth (km)	L (km)	H (km)	Dip (°)	Strike (°)	λ_3 (km ²)
I (Chihshang Fault)	C ₂	16244	121.344	23.090	18.3	45.6	16.0	47.6	14.3	3.3626
II (Chihshang Fault)	C ₂₁	12227	121.353	23.140	17.9	27.4	15.0	54.3	14.9	1.8778
	C ₂₂	2463	121.305	22.894	19.6	18.0	12.5	42.5	2.3	2.5074

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3.3 Case 3: clouds of earthquake hypocenters associated with a strike-slip fault (California, USA)

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We apply the proposed methodology to the most recent swarm occurred in Cahuilla Valley (California, USA), in the area between the Elsinore and San Jacinto strike-slip faults (Ross et al., 2020, Cochran et al., 2023). The swarm seismicity is considered to be controlled by hot fluid circulation, which causes characteristic hypocenter migration patterns with a big number of earthquakes in a relatively small volume (Hauksson et al., 2019; Ross et al., 2020; Cochran et al., 2023). We use the high-resolution catalog available at Caltech (2020), which consists of 22700 events spanning from 2016-01-01 to 2019-06-28.

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Fig. 5a shows a DBSCAN cluster solution with $\varepsilon = 0.5$ km and $Z = 100$. The algorithm identifies six clusters and discards about 5% of events classified as noise (gray points in Fig. 5a). We apply PCA only to the biggest first-order cluster C_1 (see Fig. 5b) containing nearly all earthquakes (19621 events) and related to a strike-slip fault. Fig. 5c shows the reachability plot of C_1 , with the cut line $\varepsilon = 0.21$ km that identifies several valleys associated to second-order clusters. By applying PCA, we retrieved the geometrical parameters reported in Table 3. The covariance matrices of C_1 and C_{11} have the largest eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 of the order of about 1 km, i.e. much larger than relative horizontal and vertical errors (38 m and 87 m, respectively (Ross et al., 2020)). This is the reason why an estimate of the related planar surfaces is attempted even if in both cases the third eigenvalue λ_3 is less than the resolution error (see Table 3). Note that the third eigenvalues of all the remaining second-order clusters are much smaller than the resolution error. Therefore, the related seismicity stays unclassified.

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315 **Figure 5.** A workflow application to Cahuilla dataset. **a** A DBSCAN solution illuminating
316 six earthquake clusters in Cahuilla Valley ($Z = 100$ and $\varepsilon = 0.5$ km). **b** First-order cluster C_1
317 with the planar surface retrieved by PCA. **c** Reachability plot of C_1 with the cut line $\varepsilon = 0.21$
318 km. **d** DBSCAN solution ($Z = 100$ and $\varepsilon = 0.21$ km) with second-order clusters. Earthquakes
319 classified as noise points are shown only in the first panel in gray color.

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322 **Table 3** Geometrical parameters from PCA analysis applied to first-order cluster C_1 and
323 related second-order clusters shown in Fig. 5b and Fig. 5d. Longitude, Latitude and Depth are
324 those of the barycenter of the clusters.

325

Cluster order	Symbol	N	Longitude (°)	Latitude (°)	Depth (km)	L (km)	H (km)	Dip (°)	Strike (°)	λ_3 (km ²)
I (Cahuilla Fault)	C_1	19621	-116.790	33.503	6.8	3.5	3.2	79.9	344	0.015
II (Cahuilla Fault)	C_{11}	14108	-116.789	33.501	6.8	3.4	2.7	80.7	345	0.005
	C_{12}	950	-116.792	33.508	7.0	-	-	-	-	0.001
	C_{13}	737	-116.796	33.518	6.7	-	-	-	-	0.001
	C_{14}	501	-116.789	33.515	8.4	-	-	-	-	3.e-04
	C_{15}	356	-116.786	33.488	6.0	-	-	-	-	0.002

326

327 4 Comparison between calculated planar features and fault focal mechanisms

328 In all areas, orientation of planes retrieved from PCA analysis on both first- and
329 second-order clusters shows a good fit with that derived from nodal planes of focal

330 mechanisms calculated for the same clusters (see Table 4). This suggests that the
 331 reconstructed planar features for the first-order clusters can be interpreted as fault surfaces,
 332 while those within second-order clusters as fault segments within the embedding fault
 333 surface.

334 Within the same first-order cluster, a planar feature output of PCA analysis before applying
 335 OPTICS can be interpreted as a fault surface with a thickness given by the square root of λ_3 ,
 336 while planes output of PCA analysis after OPTICS can be interpreted as fault segments
 337 contained within the fault surface.

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339 **Table 4** Comparison between the estimated fault parameters and those retrieved by focal
 340 mechanisms.

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Case 1: extensional faults (Italy dataset)						
L'Aquila Fault						
Fault angles	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (I-order)	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (II-order)	Brunsvik et al., 2021	Lavecchia et al., 2012	Chiaraluce, 2012	Boncio et al., 2010
Dip (°)	~39	~30 – 49	~42.6	~45	~48	
Strike (°)	~N144	~N130 – N142	~N143	~N140	~N137	N130 - N140
Campotosto Fault						
Dip (°)	~20	~25 – 37		~50	~20 ~45 – 50	
Strike (°)	~N151	~N137-147	~N150	N140-150		
Case 2: reverse faults (Taiwan dataset)						
Chihshang fault						
Fault angles	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (I-order)	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (II-order)	Angelier et al., 2001	Kuochen et al., 2007	Chen et al., 2008	
Dip (°)	~48	~42-54	~39-45	~45	~45-50	
Strike (°)	~N14E	~N2-15E	~N18E	N36.5E		
Case 3: strike-slip faults (California dataset)						
Cahuilla fault						
Fault angles	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (I-order)	DBSCAN+OPTICS +PCA (II-order)	Ross et al., 2020	Cochran et al., 2023		
Dip (°)	~80	~81	~70/80	82		
Strike (°)	344	345	-	343		

342

343 5 Discussion

344 We have presented a new methodology with a dual purpose of illuminating the main
 345 fault surfaces within hypocenter clouds and investigating the possible occurrence of a
 346 hierarchical segmentation within them. The results obtained for the L'Aquila seismic
 347 sequence show that starting from a DBSCAN solution in the CR allows us to naturally
 348 illuminate the main faults (L'Aquila Fault and Campotosto Fault) at the first step as first-
 349 order structures. Note that this output is found without the application of any data filter, i.e.
 350 we used all data without reduction on magnitudes or spatial extension. The same
 351 consideration holds also for the Taiwan and Cahuilla datasets.

352 The Cahuilla dataset is unique, with approximately 86% of the data concentrated in a
 353 relatively small area compared to other analyzed seismic sequences. For this reason, an initial

354 choice of DBSCAN parameters was made just outside the CR, solely for the purpose of
355 describing the densest area of hypocenters corresponding to the listric fault identified in the
356 literature as the first-order cluster. In fact, based on how the CR is defined (Piegari et al.,
357 2022), if the choice of parameters falls within the CR, the largest cluster must contain less
358 than 60% of the data. However, we would like to clarify that if a choice of parameters had
359 been made within the CR, the reachability plot would have still identified the same fault
360 segments, and the only thing that would have changed is the order numbering. This means
361 that for a solution in the CR the cluster C_{11} of Fig. 5d would become the cluster C_1 keeping
362 its shape essentially unchanged.

363 The reachability plots for the other two datasets show a more articulated spatial distribution
364 of earthquakes. In particular, within the first-order Campotosto cluster, four second-order
365 valleys are well evident. They show that the first-order structure is actually not a single
366 surface but it is composed by four main planar segments with different dips that combined
367 together give shape to a listric geometry, in accordance with what derived from other data
368 sources (Chiaraluce et al., 2011). A curved surface also describes the large Chihshang fault
369 (e.g., Kuo-Chen et al., 2007) In this case, the application of the proposed workflow allows us
370 to identify two second-order planar segments with higher and lower dip angles in the northern
371 and southern sectors, respectively. Looking at the reachability plot in Fig. 4c, it is visible that
372 both second-order surfaces are composed of other segments related to the relative sub-
373 valleys. From the analysis of the main third-order clusters, which is reported in the supporting
374 information, a higher dip angle of about 50° is also found for the southern part of large first-
375 order fault structure.

376 Looking at the reachability plot related to the cluster C_1 associated with L'Aquila fault, third
377 order clusters are easily recognizable as valleys included in the second-order clusters C_{11} and
378 C_{12} (see Fig. 3a). The application of DBSCAN and PCA on such sub-valleys allows us to
379 investigate the geometries of the associated faults in more detail (see supporting information).
380 In particular, the analysis of the valleys of C_{11} shows that the complex morphology of the
381 associated fault can be approximated by two distinct sets of planar segments describing two
382 different types of seismicity: a shallower seismicity concentrated in an almost flat region
383 characterized by very low dip angles (about 10° , see supporting information) and a deeper
384 seismicity related to a fault segment with a vertical extension up to 10 km.

385 The identification of second and third order planar segments cannot be achieved by a single
386 run of DBSCAN but requires the visual inspection of the reachability plots for the selection
387 of the appropriate ϵ value. This is a limitation of the proposed approach, which at this stage is
388 not fully automatic. However, once the selected order to investigate is chosen, the procedure
389 is very simple and fast, providing parameters and visualization of planar surfaces in a few
390 minutes. Furthermore, the computation of the reachability plot is not dependent on the choice
391 of input parameter values of DBSCAN, but rather reflects the data distribution in space, so
392 the determination of the hierarchy of fault segments is not operator-dependent but solely
393 based on the data.

394 Another limitation of the workflow is related to the use of Euclidean distance as the metric to
395 compute the similarity between data. Since the UTM coordinate system uses map projections,
396 a relative location error is introduced due to the Earth's curvature. Such an error is usually
397 negligible if the investigated hypocenter distribution extends within the same UTM zone, as
398 in the cases examined in the paper. A further element to improve the workflow is the
399 introduction of uncertainty of attributing earthquakes to clusters. With the goal to keep the
400 approach simple, the output of the presented workflow is an earthquake classification where
401 each hypocenter is strictly assigned to a planar segment or belongs to uncategorized

402 seismicity. Note that a percentage of earthquakes associated to first-order planar surfaces
403 becomes uncategorized when second-order structures are investigated and the same happens
404 when third or higher-order clusters are searched.

405 Overall, the workflow presented in this article has proven to be a valuable tool for roughly
406 illuminating fault surfaces and their segmented nature. However, it is important to note here
407 that this workflow, while providing valuable information for the degree of segmentation of a
408 fault, has certain limitations. For instance, the 3D shape of the tip lines (i.e., boundaries of a
409 fault at which its displacement is null) bounding the automatically retrieved fault surfaces and
410 segments are rectilinear and may differ from their actual shapes. Furthermore, the
411 computation of planar surfaces has been conducted under the assumption of earthquakes
412 uniformly distributing over the fault, which may lead to an inaccurate evaluation of fault
413 length and width. Also, this workflow assumes that the entirety of a fault surface/segments is
414 active, and therefore illuminated by earthquake hypocentres. However, this may not be the
415 case and consequently the automatically retrieved faults may be incomplete surfaces.
416 Therefore, it is essential to exercise caution when using these results. Instead, we recommend
417 using them as proxies to further define fault geometries accurately, a task best carried out by
418 a structural geologist familiar with the 3D geometrical templates of segmented faults, as well
419 as with the geometrical peculiarities of faults of an area.

420 To end, we outline some perspectives for the future use of the workflow. The study of the
421 spatio-temporal variations of the frequency-magnitude distributions related to the various
422 clusters/segments can provide important implications for seismic hazard forecasting
423 (Herrmann et al., 2022). Furthermore, by splitting the examined hypocenter distribution in
424 different periods, co-seismic interactions between fault segments of different order could be
425 investigated for tracking possible routes of 4D progression of ruptures during an earthquake.

426

427 **6 Conclusions**

428 We propose a methodology exclusively based on unsupervised machine learning
429 algorithms to obtain an unbiased reconstruction of main faults and their hierarchical
430 segmentation within clouds of earthquake hypocenters. We applied the method to seismic
431 events occurred along faults with diverse kinematics and we were able to estimate fault
432 parameters consistent with those already known by focal mechanisms.

433 The method allows the reconstruction of faults at multiple scales. The largest one depends on
434 the specific hypocenter distribution and it is bound by the longest pattern of approximately
435 equal dense regions of earthquakes. The lowest one is related to the resolution error.

436 Iterative loops of DBSCAN, OPTICS and PCA first allow the identification of the largest
437 faults and then illuminate the related segments of decreasing sizes. The retrieved planar
438 surfaces are not randomly oriented but have overall a very similar orientation to the fault
439 orientation that can be derived from earthquake focal mechanisms calculated from the same
440 earthquake clusters. The combined analysis of the orientations, sizes and spatial arrangements
441 of the retrieved fault segments, by also taking into account the temporal dimension, is a
442 promising way for investigating the 4D progression of ruptures during an earthquake, with
443 important implications on short- and long- term hazard forecasting.

444

445 **Conflict of Interest**

446 The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this study.

447

448 **Data Availability Statement**

449 L'Aquila seismic sequence dataset is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/4036248>; Cahuilla

450 dataset is available at <https://scedc.caltech.edu/data/cahuilla-swarm.html>

451 The three datasets used in this study are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/8210903>. The

452 code to perform the cluster and principal component analyses is implemented in MATLAB

453 environment and makes use of software packages available in the Statistics and Machine

454 Learning Toolbox of MATLAB R2023a. It is permanently stored in the repository

455 <https://zenodo.org/record/8211032> (Piegarì et al., 2023b). It is also publicly available on Github

456 under the GPL-3.0 license: https://github.com/epiegarì/hypo_clustering

457

458 **Acknowledgements**

459 We wish to thank two anonymous reviewers for their useful suggestions and comments,

460 which definitely helped improving the manuscript. G.C. acknowledges Dennis Brown, Hao

461 Kuo-Chen, and Vincent Roche for several discussions on the topic of this paper.

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